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**ESTIMATION OF THE DETERMINANTS OF THE SYSTEM OF
MANAGEMENT BY THE REGION'S NATURE AND RECREATION
POTENTIAL AND SEARCH OF POSSIBILITIES FOR INNOVATIONS**

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Анотація. Сучасне управління регіоном має бути спрямоване на забезпечення його прогресивного розвитку. Враховуючи сучасні внутрішні умови в країні, а саме низьку платоспроможність населення та досягнення нестабільності, це можливо за рахунок кращого управління внутрішнім регіональним потенціалом. Ось чому в даний час все більше людей залучаються до використання природного та рекреаційного потенціалу, доступного в регіоні як державним, так і приватним структурам.

Здійснено оцінку детермінант системи управління природно-рекреаційним потенціалом регіону та окреслено потенціали виробництва та впровадження інновацій. На основі опрацювання існуючих наукових дослідників авторське трактування сутності природно-рекреаційного потенціалу як поєднання природних рекреаційних ресурсів, умов та стану довкілля регіону, що впливає, використовується або може бути використане для розвитку рекреаційних заходів, здатних створювати позитивні враження, емоції, які є основою для відновлення фізичних і духовних сил людини. Прогресивний розвиток регіону забезпечує функціонування ефективної системи управління природним та рекреаційним потенціалом у ринковому середовищі. У системі управління природним та рекреаційним потенціалом регіону визначено ресурсні, інфраструктурні, екологічні та соціально-економічні компоненти. Кожен із компонентів описується системою показників, які характеризують компоненти, стан та результати роботи системи природно-рекреаційного потенціалу. Визначено детермінанти

функціонування ефективної системи управління природно-рекреаційним потенціалом регіону. Визначені кореляційні залежності між детермінантами та факторами системи управління, що дозволило оцінити тісність зв'язку між ними, їх впливи та пріоритетні, які вони формують. Проведена оцінка детермінант природокористувально-рекреаційного потенціалу є основою для побудови планів, прогнозів та сценаріїв прогресивного розвитку регіону, які стануть основою для подальших досліджень.

Ключові слова: природний та рекреаційний потенціал, управління природним та рекреаційним потенціалом, детермінанти, компонент, показник.

Annotation. The estimation of the determinants of the system of management of the natural and recreational potential of the region is carried out and the potential opportunities for production and implementation of innovations are outlined. On the basis of elaboration of existing scientific researches, the author's interpretation of the essence of the nature-recreational potential as a combination of natural recreational resources, conditions and the state of the environment of the region, which influence, is used or can be used for the development of recreational activities that can create positive impressions, emotions that is the basis for the restoration of the physical and spiritual forces of man. It is proved that in the economic sense, the natural and recreational potential in the market conditions is capitalized which allows organizers of recreational activities to profit. The subject of the capitalization of nature-recreational potential is the formation of positive impressions, emotions, which are the basis for the restoration of the physical and spiritual forces of man and for the consumption of which they can pay or not pay directly the corresponding funds. The process of capitalizing the nature-recreational potential requires not just management, but building a whole system, moreover, effective. An effective system of management of nature-recreational potential is one that provides capitalization of nature-recreational potential for socio-commercial purposes (tourist-recreational, research and cognitive, etc.) and maximizes socio-economic benefits in the region (socio-economic efficiency) and conservation environment and minimization of negative environmental impacts (ecological efficiency). It is the functioning of an effective management system for natural and recreational potential in a market environment that ensures the progressive development of the region. In the system of management of natural and recreational potential of the region, the following components are identified as resource, infrastructure, ecological and socio-economic. Each of the components is described by a system of indicators (indicators) that characterize the components, state and results of the system of management of nature-recreational potential. The determinants of the functioning of an effective system of management of the natural and recreational potential of the region are identified, namely: the number of persons accommodated in hotels and similar means of accommodation, the number of persons serviced by specialized accommodation facilities, the number of tourists served by tourism activity subjects, the number of people served in agrarian areas of the region, number of tourists. In this work, correlation dependencies between determinants and control system factors were created, which made it possible to estimate the tightness of the connection between them, their influence and the priority ones that they form. The expediency of accentuating the strategies and mechanisms of object management of the natural and

recreational potential of territories, which is a prerequisite for the formation and implementation of innovations. The conducted assessment of the determinants of the system of management of nature-recreational potential is the basis for constructing plans, forecasts and scenarios for the progressive development of the region, which will be the basis for further research.

Keywords: natural and recreational potential, management of the natural and recreational potential, determinants, component, indicator

Introduction.

Formulation of the problem. The modern management of the region should be aimed at ensuring its progressive development. Taking into account the current internal conditions in the country namely the low solvency of the population and instability achievement of this is possible at the expense to better management of the internal regional potential. That is why, nowadays, more and more people are involved in the use of natural and recreational potential available in the region to both public and private structures.

Analysis of research and publications. The question of the practice of developing and discovering natural and recreational potential of the regions for the market period was devoted to the scientific achievements of domestic scientists of the Lviv branch of the Institute of Economics of the Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (now - the Institute of Regional Studies of the National Academy of Sciences). M. Dolishniy, L. Grinov, V. Kravtsev, S. Kuzyk (1995) [1] substantiated theoretical and applied aspects of recreational activity, expediency of using programmatic-target planning and ways to improve management of this sphere of activity, substantiated the conceptual foundations of perspective development of recreational activity in Western Ukraine, in particular, Carpathian region.

In the period of transformations, Lviv scientists V. Kravtsiv, Yu. Stadnytskyi, P. Zhuk (2010) [2] proposed market mechanisms in the field of nature management (the concept of modernization), which absorbed the best domestic and foreign experience of using economic instruments in the use, protection and reproduction of natural recreational resources. The work by G. Shevchenko (2008) [3] is devoted to the problem of the organizational and economic mechanism of formation and use of the natural and recreational potential of the territory (Sumy region), and the mechanisms of formation and implementation of the policy of development of recreational nature use of the Volyn region of labor Z. Gerasymchuk, N. Kolenda, L. Cherchyk (2007) [4], Z. Gerasymchuk, M. Gladina (2006) [5].

In addition, a significant part of foreign and domestic researchers pays considerable attention to the study of nature conservation and recreational activities, namely E. Vlasova, L. Poliakova (2011) [6], E. Zaliznyak (2012) [7], N. Reimers, A. Yablokov (1982) [8]. Despite the considerable number of works of domestic and foreign scientists, special attention is required to study the results of the functioning of the regional system of management of natural and recreational potential with the allocation of component structure and components, indicators that characterize it, the main determinants that determine its effectiveness.

The aim of the article is an assessment of the determinants of the management system and the search for opportunities for implementation of innovations in the management of the natural and recreational potential of the region-Rivne in order to ensure its progressive development in the future.

Main results of the study.

Studying of scientific literature gives the right to denote that among researchers there is no unanimity in the interpretation of the nature of nature and recreational potential. It is on the basis of the elaboration of existing research that we offer under the natural and recreational potential to understand the totality of natural recreational resources, conditions and the state of the environment of the region that influence. They can be used to develop recreational activities that can form positive impressions, emotions, which are the basis for the restoration of the physical and spiritual forces of man.

In the economic sense, the natural and recreational potential in the market conditions takes an advantage that enables organizers of recreational activities to profit. The subject of the capitalization of nature and recreational potential is the formation of positive impressions, emotions, which are the basis for the restoration of the physical and spiritual forces of man and for the consumption of which they can pay or not pay directly the corresponding funds. Of course, the process of capitalizing the nature and recreational potential requires not just to manage it, but the creation and operation of the appropriate infrastructure.

In modern conditions, requirements for rational use of nature, in particular regarding the preservation and reproduction of natural resources, are increasing and thus the system of management of natural and recreational potential is being modernized. It is based on the recognition of the interconnection of all components of the process and the results of management as well as the need to ensure sustainable and balanced social and economic, ecological, and infrastructure development of the region. Under the existing effective system of management of nature and recreational potential we understand something that provides the capitalization of nature and recreational potential for social and commercial purposes (tourist-recreational, research and cognitive, etc.) and maximizes social and economic benefits in the region (social and economic efficiency) and preservation of the environment and minimization of negative environmental consequences (ecological efficiency). We believe that the main determinants of the process of capitalizing the nature and recreational potential and generating cash flows from the functioning of an effective management system for the natural and recreational potential of the region are the following:

1. number of persons accommodated in hotels and similar means of accommodation,
2. number of persons serviced by specialized means of placement,
3. number of tourists served by the subjects of tourism activity,
4. number of persons serviced in agrarian farms of the region,
5. number of tourists.

We propose to evaluate the system of management of the nature and recreational potential of the region. Rivne is the region on such basic structural components as resource, infrastructure, ecological and social and economic ones (Table 1).

Table 1 - Composition of the components for assessing the management system of the natural and recreational potential of the region (source: own development of authors)

Composition	Components
Resource	Nature Reserve Fund
	Hunting economy
	Water objects
Infrastructure	Accommodation facilities
	Cultural and artistic institutions
	Ways of communication
Ecological	Emissions of pollutants into the air and water objects
	Waste and handling
Social and economic	Economic indicators of the region's development
	Indicators of the social status of the region

Resource component of the system of management of nature and recreational potential is a set of indicators that characterize the actual natural and recreational potential of the region. Due to the availability of natural recreational facilities such as mineral water deposits, unique natural landscapes, this area a priori is of interest to tourists, which leads to opportunities for capitalization of resources. The components of the resource combine the indicators of the state of the nature reserve fund (natural reserves, national natural and regional landscape parks, nature reserves, nature monuments, dendrological and zoological parks, parks-monuments of landscape architecture, national and local nature reserves importance), hunting facilities and recreational water resources (mineral waters, beaches) that provide recreation opportunities for people. In a dynamic comparison the resource component allows us to assess the changes in the state of resources, and, hence, the intensity of the management system processes aimed at maintaining and developing natural resource potential.

The infrastructure component reflects the "development" of the nature and recreational potential and includes both indicators that quantitatively characterize the network and ramification of accommodation facilities (hotels and similar accommodation facilities, specialized accommodation facilities, agro-homesteads) and related additional cultural institutions that promote positive impressions of recreation (theaters, museums, concert organizations, libraries, clubs, film showers), transport links, and indicators that measure intensity and quality component of their use (attendance). Infrastructure development is an important means to increase not only the tourist attractiveness of the territory, but also its socio-economic status as a whole. In order to raise the level of tourist attractiveness of the region, the most natural and recreational resources are not enough. Indeed, according to O.V. Muzychenko-Kozlovskaya (2012) [9, p.38] "... a large number of tourists area where there are no modern hotels or bad roads, can not attract, but because of high profits, tourism will not bring." Therefore, changes in the indicators of the dynamics in the context of the

research allow to assess the level of "development" of the potential, and the intensity of its development, and the quality of management of components.

The ecological component combines the indicators characterizing the mutual influence of the results of the region's development and the nature and recreational potential on the environment, and vice versa, since the implementation of measures for environmental protection and enhancement of its quality not only promotes the development of tourism, but also allows other social and economic effects to be obtained. The main semantic value of this component is the demonstration of the impact of the clean environment and the efforts of the community in its support for the tourist attractiveness of the region.

The social and economic component demonstrates the interrelation of the development of the region and the capitalization of nature and recreational potential through the indicators of the formation and use of economic resources and the provision of social effects.

Each of the components is described by a system of indicators (indicators) that characterize the components, state and results of the system of management of nature-recreational potential. Based on the generalization of the existing statistical datas, regional, data of the Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration, we have formed an indicative base for assessing the management system for the natural and recreational potential of Rivne Oblast in tabl. 2

Table 2. -Indicative base for assessment of the management system for natural and recreational potential of the Rivne region (source: own development of authors)

Components	Indicators	Notes
Resource component		
Nature Reserve Fund	Forests and forest covered areas	Input
	Opened wetlands	Input
	Number of objects of nature reserve fund (NFP)	Input.
	Costs for the maintenance of objects of the nature reserve fund (NRF) (of national importance)	Input
	The number of employees employed in the FPF	Input
	Number of visitors to the nature reserve fund objects	Result.
	Number of tourist routes covered on the Internet	Input/Result.
	Number of cultural and artistic events	Input/Result
Hunting economy	Number of hunting farms	Input
	Area of hunting areas	Input
	Number of employees in hunting farms	Input
	Total cost of hunting	Input
	Income from hunting	Result.

	Payback for hunting	Result.
Water objects	Areas covered with surface waters	Input
	Number of sections of mineral groundwater	Input
	Extraction of mineral water	Result.
	Number of equipped beaches	Input/ Result.
Infrastructure component		
Accommodation facilities	The number of collective accommodation facilities (CAF)	Input
	Number of persons placed in collective accommodation facilities	Result.
	Number of agro farmsteads	Input
	Number of people placed in agro-homesteads	Result.
Culture and arts establishments	Number of theaters	Input
	Number of visitors to theaters	Result.
	Number of concert organizations	Input
	Number of visitors to concert organizations	Result.
	Number of museums	Input
	Number of visits to museums	Result.
	Libraries	Input
	Library Foundation	Result.
	Movie Demos	Input
	Number of movie sessions	Result.
	Club establishments	Input
Places in clubs	Result.	
Ways of communication	Operating length of railways	Input
	Length of public roads with hard cover	Input
	Transportation of passengers by rail and road	Result.
Екологічна компонента		
Wastes of pollutants into the air and water objects	Density of emissions of pollutants into atmospheric air	Input
	Reset contaminated return water without cleaning in surface water objects	Input
	Number of environmental measures	Result.
	Power of treatment facilities	Result.
	Capital investment and current environmental costs (CEC)	Result.
Waste and handling them	Volumes of waste generation	Input
	Volumes of waste accumulation	Input

	Recycling, waste disposal	Result.
	Number of arranged landfills and landfills for the disposal of solid household waste	Result.
Socialn and economic component		
Indicators of economic development	Consumer price index	Result.
	Volume of sales of products by type of activity "Temporary placement and organization of trade"	Result.
	Share of profitable enterprises by type of activity	Result.
	Capital investment by type of activity	Result.
	Charges and fees for the special use of natural resources	Result.
	Tourist tax	Result.
	The share of the actual payment of environmental tax	Result.
	Number of EDRPOU entities	Result.
	Available income per 1 person	Result.
Indicators of social status	Employment of the population	Result.
	The need for employers in workers to replace vacancies by type of activity "Temporary placement and organization of trade"	Result.
	Employed by type of activity	Result.
	Average month salary of full-time employees by type of activity	Result.
	Population incidence (for the first time illnesses were detected)	Result.
	Number of detected crimes	Result.

Indicators of the number of tourist routes covered in the Internet, cultural and artistic activities (resource component), equipped beaches (infrastructure component) are identified as inputs in the assessment of the system of management of nature-recreational potential, since they, in combination with others, form and complement the environment and opportunities its capitalization, but in the context of evaluating the effectiveness of the system of management of nature and recreational potential and the result of its capitalization and classification.

The significance of the influence of these factors on the determinants of the system of management of the natural and recreational potential of the region is estimated by the results of a correlation analysis conducted according to the data for 2010-2015 and interpreted by the values of the correlation coefficient according to the Chaddock scale. The results of the analysis indicated a direct and feedback relationship between the factors and the differences in the importance of their influence on various determinants. In turn, this means that for the functioning and development of the tourism and recreation industry there is not enough resource potential, development of all tangent

industries, especially infrastructure and rational use of nature and environmental protection is necessary. The feedback between the indicators is, to a greater extent, the consequence of their declining dynamics during the period under study.

The determinant (the number of people served by hotels and similar accommodation facilities) is strongly influenced by the input indicators of the resource (the number of ILC facilities, the number of hunting facilities, the number of mineral water sections) and the environmental (volume of generation and accumulation of waste) component. Strong feedback is also observed with the indicators of the resource (the area of hunting grounds, the number of equipped beaches, the volume of mineral water extraction, the number of visitors to the ILC) and the infrastructure (number of libraries, operating length of the railways) component (Table 3).

Table 3 - Assessment of the connection between the determinant (the number of persons accommodated in hotels and similar means of accommodation) and factors of the system of management of natural and recreational potential of the region

(source: formed by the authors according to the data of the Main Department of Statistics in the Rivne region [10], National report on the state of the natural environment in Ukraine in 2015 [11], Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration [12])

Direct connection	Feedback
<i>Weak connection (0,1 < r < 0,3)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - capacity of treatment facilities, - volumes of utilization and disposal of waste, - visiting concert organizations, - the length of the roads with hard cover, - passenger transportation by rail and road, - consumer price index. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - payback of the hunting economy, - the density of emissions into the atmosphere, - capital investments by type of activity, - employment by type of activity <p>"Temporary placement and organization of trade".</p>
<i>Moderate connection (0,3 < r < 0,5)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - open wetlands - maintenance costs for the NFP, - number of employees in hunting farms, - fee for special use of natural resources, - number of subjects of the USREOU,- кількість виявлених злочинів. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - discharging of contaminated return water without purification in surface water objects, - number of environmental measures, - the number of agro farmsteads - library fund.
<i>Significant connection (0,5 < r < 0,7)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - forests and forest cover areas - areas covered with surface waters, - number of tourist routes, - number of cultural and artistic events, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of employees employed in the FPF, - morbidity of the population.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - expenses for hunting, - income from hunting, - share of profitable enterprises by type of activity, - tourist tax, - Employed by type of activity. 	
<p><i>Strong connection (0,7<r<0,9)</i></p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of FPF objects, - number of hunting facilities, - number of mineral water sections, - number of collective accommodation facilities, - capital investments and current costs of NPS protection, - volumes of waste generation, - volumes of waste accumulation, - visiting theaters - visiting museums - visiting cinema sessions - the number of clubs, - available income per 1 person - the need for employers in workers to replace job vacancies by type of activity, - Average monthly salary of full-time employees by type of activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of visitors to the NFP, - area of hunting grounds, - the number of equipped beaches, - volumes of extraction of mineral waters, - the number of libraries - operating length of railways, - volume of sold products by type of activity "Temporary placement and organization of trade".
<p><i>Very strong connection (r>0,9)</i></p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the capacity of club facilities.

Very strong feedback between the determinants (the number of persons accommodated in hotels and similar facilities) and the capacity of club facilities. At the same time, there is a weak and moderate relationship with other environmental indicators (input: the density of emissions into the air, the discharge of contaminated water without cleaning in surface water bodies; the resulting: the capacity of wastewater treatment facilities, the volume of utilization and disposal of waste, the number of environmental measures), resource - in terms of the availability of wetlands, the state of the NFP (indexes of maintenance costs), socio-economic (consumer price index, capital investment and employment by type of activity "Temporary placement and organization of trade", fees for special use of natural resources, number of EDRPOU entities, number of detected crimes) and infrastructure (visit to concert organizations, carriage of passengers by road and rail transport) component

The number of tourist routes, cultural and artistic activities, the presence of forests and water bodies are influential but not decisive factors for visiting the area by people staying in hotels and similar accommodation facilities. Tourism and recreation are not

always the main purpose of such visitors, but are part of the overall impression and can influence the decision on subsequent visits.

Detected correlation dependencies indicate that the nature reserve fund, hunting, mineral waters and clean environments, beaches and railways are one of the main factors influencing the number of people staying in hotels and similar accommodation facilities. The change in their number also involves visiting cultural and artistic events and institutions, sales volumes in the industry, available income of the population, demand for labor and salaries of full-time employees. It means that the development of the hotel industry gives a tangible positive social and economic effect in the region, and one of the effective directions of its development is taking into account the features and use of natural and recreational resources of the territory.

In contrast, the assessment of the connection of the following determinants of the system of management of nature-recreational potential (the number of persons serviced in specialized means of accommodation) with factors is less significant and numeric (Table 4).

Table 4 - Evaluation of the connection between the determinant (the number of persons serviced by specialized means of placement) and factors of the system of management of the natural and recreational potential of the region (source: formed by the authors according to the data of the Main Department of Statistics in the Rivne region [10], National report on the state of the natural environment in Ukraine in 2015 [11], Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration [12])

Direct connection	Feedback
<i>Weak connection (0,1 < r < 0,3)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -the number of equipped beaches, - operating length of railways, - length of roads, - morbidity of the population - number of visitors to the NFP, - library fund - number of environmental measures, -the volume of waste generation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of hunting facilities, - number of collective accommodation facilities, - the number of libraries - the number of movie demonstrators - the number of clubs, - the need for employers in workers by type of activity, - employed by sphere of activity, - proceeds from the management of the hunting economy.
<i>Moderate connection (0,3 < r < 0,5)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintenance costs for the NFP, - the number of employees employed in the FPF, - area of hunting grounds, - areas covered with surface waters, - the number of agro farmsteads - capital investments by type of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of FPF objects, - number of tourist routes, - number of cultural and artistic events, - number of mineral water sections, - number of museums - consumer price index

activity, Employment of the population by type of activity - number of places in clubs, - carriage of passengers by road and rail, - density of emissions into the atmosphere, - the amount of waste disposal and disposal.	- the number of detected crimes; - number of visits to theaters, - number of visits to museums, - number of visits to cinema sessions - Discharge of contaminated return water without cleaning in surface water objects.
<i>Significant connection ($0,5 < r < 0,7$)</i>	
- volumes of extraction of mineral waters, - payments for the special use of natural resources, - number of subjects of the USREOU.	- forests and forest cover areas - open wetlands - number of hunters. state tvakh - tourist tax, - average monthly salary of full-time employees by type of activity, - the capacity of the treatment facilities.
<i>Strong connection ($0,7 < r < 0,9$)</i>	
- payback of the hunting economy.	- expenses for hunting, - share of profitable enterprises by type of activity, - available income per 1 person; - volumes of waste accumulation, - capital investments and current costs of NPP protection.
<i>Very strong connection ($r > 0,9$)</i>	
	- number of visitors to concert organizations

This type of recreation is aimed at supporting and restoring the forces and health of people and is objectively related to the availability and state of the relevant natural and recreational resources, which confirms the established significant and strong correlation with the indicators of the resource (forests and forest cover area, open wetlands, mineral water extraction) and the ecological component (capacity of wastewater treatment facilities, waste accumulation, capital investment, and running costs of NPPs). The weak and moderate relationship with the indicators of the number of cultural and artistic institutions and activities, water facilities and equipped beaches, hunting facilities and routes and most indicators of social status indicate the health priorities of this group of people and the social and commercial purpose of business facilities accommodation, which contributes to the development of the relevant infrastructure (the number of EDRPOU entities) and to increase the incomes of the population. Significant and strong correlation with the performance indicators of the hunting economy (the number of

employees in the hunting industry, costs and payback) is indicative of alternative, rather than parallel, directions of development of both branches (sanatorium and resort health improvement and treatment and hunting). A very strong (though inverse) connection between the number of persons serviced in specialized means of accommodation and the number of visits to concerts demonstrates the established traditions of leisure organization in recreation and recreation facilities.

The determinant (the number of tourists traveled by foreign tourists and domestic tourists) is most correlated (strong and very strong connection) with the already described indicators of the resource and ecological component, namely, the availability and volumes of mineral water extraction and the costs of hunting and volumes of accumulated waste (Table 5).

Table 5 - Evaluation of the connection between the determinant (the number of domestic and foreign tourists served by the subjects of tourism activity) and factors of the management system of the natural and recreational potential of the region(source: formed by the authors according to the data of the Main Department of Statistics in the Rivne region [10], National report on the state of the natural environment in Ukraine in 2015 [11], Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration [12])

Direct connection	Feedback
<i>Weak connection (0,1 < r < 0,3)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consumer price index - number of environmental measures, - length of highways - costs for the maintenance of PZF. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - payments for the special use of natural resources, - volumes of utilization and disposal of waste, - density of emissions into the atmosphere, - capacity of treatment facilities, - territories covered with surface waters.
<i>Moderate connection (0,3 < r < 0,5)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - employment by type of activity, - payback of the hunting economy, - area of hunting grounds. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - share of profitable enterprises by type of activity, - capital investments by type of activity, - number of subjects of the USREOU, - employment of employees by type of activity, - the number of detected crimes; - number of concert visits - carriage of passengers by road and rail, - open wetlands.
<i>Significant connection (0,5 < r < 0,7)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volume of sold products by type of activity, - number of visitors to the NFP, - library fund - discharging of contaminated return 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tourist tax, - the need for employers in workers by type of activity, - proceeds from the management of the hunting economy,

water without purification in surface water objects, - the number of libraries - the number of beaches equipped.	- number of visits to museums, - number of visits to cinema sessions - capital investments and current costs of NPS protection, - volumes of waste generation, - number of museums - the number of clubs, - the forests and the forest covered the area, - the number of FPF objects, - number of tourist routes, number of cultural and artistic events, - number of hunting facilities, - number of employees in the hunting industry.
<i>Strong connection (0,7<r<0,9)</i>	
- morbidity of the population - volumes of mineral water extraction, - the number of agro farmsteads - operating length of railways.	- available income per 1 person; - average monthly salary by type of activity - number of visits to cinema sessions - quantity of CZR, - costs of hunting.
<i>Very strong connection (r>0,9)</i>	
- number of places in clubs, - number of employees employed in the FPF.	- number of visits to theaters, - volumes of waste accumulation, - number of mineral water sections.

For the servicing of tourists, it is important to have an adequate infrastructure for accommodation and transport which shows a strong and very strong connection with the numbers of CZR and agro-holdings, available railroad connections. Contrary to the established assertion the presence of water bodies, (areas covered with surface waters), air purity (density of atmospheric emissions) and highways (length of highways) are not a priority for tourists visiting Rivne region, but the peculiar is the presence of a strong connection between the number tourists and the morbidity of the population. The main result of strongly correlated indicators is the visit to theaters and cinema sessions, the number of places in clubs, the available income of the population and the average monthly salary by type of activity. There is also a strong link between the number of tourists and fishermen and the cost of hunting (state expenditures), because in this context, tourists form a solvent demand, which stipulates the need for servicing the NFP and the ability to maintain a hunting economy.

Green tourism is focused on the availability and use of nature and recreational potential which confirms the established very strong and strong link between the determinant (the number of people located in agro-homesteads) and the potential components (forest and marsh resources, volumes of mineral water extraction, the number of hunting farms and objects of the FPF, equipped with beaches), infrastructure and mechanisms for its development and capitalization (number of agro-homesteads, tourist routes and cultural and artistic events and facilities, their visits), environmental

indicators (volumes of accumulation of waste and capital investments, and current expenses for the protection of NPPs) (Table 6) . It is also worth noting that in this system correlation dependencies are most strongly and very strongly correlated factors.

Table 6 - Evaluation of the relationship between the determinant (the number of people hosted in agriculture) and the factors of the management system for the natural and recreational potential of the region (source: formed by the authors according to the data of the Main Department of Statistics in the Rivne region [10], National report on the state of the natural environment in Ukraine in 2015 [11], Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration [12])

Direct connection	Feedback
<i>Weak connection (0,1 < r < 0,3)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintenance costs for the NFP, - areas covered with surface waters, - capacity of treatment facilities, - the need for employers in workers by type of activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - length of roads, - discharging of contaminated return water without purification in surface water objects, - payback of the hunting state-tva - volume of sold products by type of activity, - capital investments by type of activity, - payments for the special use of natural resources
<i>Moderate connection (0,3 < r < 0,5)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volumes of waste generation, - transportation of passengers by rail, - volumes of utilization and disposal of waste, - consumer price index - number of subjects of the EDRPOU 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - operating length of railways, - morbidity of the population
<i>Significant connection (0,5 < r < 0,7)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of mineral water sections, - quantity of CZR, - number of visits to theaters, - number of concert visits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the number of employees employed in the FPF, - density of emissions into the atmosphere, - number of environmental measures, - number of visitors to the NFP
<i>Strong connection (0,7 < r < 0,9)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - open wetlands - the number of FPF objects, - number of tourist routes, - number of cultural and artistic events, - number of employees in hunting state-tvakh, - the cost of running a hunting state-tva, - number of museums 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - area of hunting grounds, - the number of equipped beaches, - the number of agro farmsteads - library fund - number of places in clubs, - employment by type of activity

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volumes of waste accumulation, - proceeds from the conduct of the hunting state-tva, - capital investments and current costs of NPS protection, - share of profitable enterprises by type of activity, - tourist tax, - available income per 1 person; - employment of employees by type of activity, - average monthly salary of full-time employees by type of activity, - Number of detected crimes 	
<i>Very strong connection ($r > 0,9$)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forests and forest cover areas - number of hunting facilities, - the number of clubs, - number of visits to museums, - number of visits to cinema sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volumes of extraction of mineral waters, - the number of libraries

The least correlated with this determinant (the number of people served in agricultural homesteads) is the availability and condition of water bodies and roads, the state of the ILC and the results of the activities of the hunting economy, and the presence of other CRAs does not constitute a serious competition for this type of tourism. The main results of strongly correlated indicators are the stimulating components of the socio-economic component (the share of profitable enterprises in the industry, tourist tax, available income, employment and employment of the population, average monthly salary of full-time employees by type of activity), disincentive indicator of the number of crimes, capital investments and current expenses for the protection of the NPS (ecological component), number of tourist routes and cultural and artistic events.

These dependencies confirm the expediency and perspective of development of rural green tourism in the region. With its parameters and configurations of nature-recreational potential, it is advisable to focus on the use of forests and the potential of the hunting economy, the introduction of new tourist routes and cultural and artistic activities, including and taking into account the historical heritage and the involvement of museums and film makers.

Unlike the previous determinants of the natural and recreational potential management system for determinants (number of tourists), the natural reserve fund (number of visits, employment and maintenance costs) is the main one (Table 7). Correlations are also strong with the availability of infrastructure (CZR and agro-homesteads) and railways, mineral water availability and the results of the hunting economy (maintenance and payback costs), and morbidity.

Table 7 - Estimation of the tightness of the link between the determinant (number of tourists) and the factors of the management system of the natural and recreational potential of the region (source: formed by the authors according to the

data of the Main Department of Statistics in the Rivne region [10], National report on the state of the natural environment in Ukraine in 2015 [11], Department of Culture and Tourism of the Rivne Regional State Administration [12])

Direct connection	Feedback
<i>Weak connection (0,1 < r < 0,3)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - areas covered with surface waters, - the number of equipped beaches, - the number of libraries - length of roads, - capacity of treatment facilities, - consumer price index - volume of sold products by type of activity, - Employment of the population by type of activity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forests and forest cover areas - the number of FPF objects, - number of hunting facilities, - area of hunting grounds, - the number of clubs, - number of environmental measures, - the volume of waste generation - number of concert visits - number of visits to cinema sessions - carriage of passengers by road and rail, - volumes of utilization and disposal of waste, - share of profitable enterprises by type of activity, - payments for special use of natural resources, - number of subjects of the USREOU, - employment of employees by type of activity, - Number of detected crimes.
<i>Moderate connection (0,3 < r < 0,5)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - volumes of mineral water extraction, - discharging of contaminated return water without purification in surface water objects, - library fund. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - open wetlands - number of tourist routes, - number of cultural and artistic events, - number of museums - density of emissions into the atmosphere, - proceeds from the conduct of the hunting state-tva, - number of visits to museums, - capital investments and current costs of NPS protection, - tourist tax, - available income per 1 person; - the need for employers in workers by type of activity, - Average monthly salary of full-time employees by type of activity.
<i>Significant connection (0,5 < r < 0,7)</i>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - maintenance costs for the NFP, - number of visitors to the NFP, - payback of the hunting economy, - the number of places in clubs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of employees in the hunting industry, - expenses for hunting, - quantity of CZR, - capital investments by type of activity.
<i>Strong connection (0,7<r<0,9)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the number of agro farmsteads - operating length of railways, -disability of the population. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of mineral water sections, - volumes of waste accumulation, -the number of theater visits.
<i>Very strong connection (r>0,9)</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - number of employees employed in the FPF. 	

However, most factors are weakly correlated with this determinant (the number of tourists). The main result of the connection is the visit to theaters. Significantly, only this determinant (the number of tourists) correlates with the indicator of capital investment by type of activity. However, the presence of significant feedback allows us to assume that the development of excursion activities is extensive and involves the use of available capacities without their modernization in perspective, which is likely to affect the reduction of the number of tourists.

Conclusions and directions of further research. Detected dependencies allowed to establish that the common factors for all determinants of the system of management of nature-recreational potential, which significantly affect the formation of the environment for attraction of tourist flows ($r_{jos} 0,7$), are the availability of and / or volumes of mineral water extraction, the volume of waste accumulation, capital investments and current NPP protection costs, ie unique natural resources and clean environments. Priority for all visitors, except for tourists, is also the presence of forest landscapes and hunting facilities, indicating the expediency of accentuating strategies and mechanisms of object management of natural and recreational potential of territories. Non-tourist flows are capital investments in the form of "Temporary placement and trade organization" and the presence of hard roads, which testify to the low level of organization and modernization of tourism activities during the period under investigation.

The conducted evaluation of the determinants of the system of management of nature and recreational potential has made it possible to identify and identify potential directions of innovation, as well as the basis for building future regional plans, forecasts and scenarios, the implementation of which will contribute to its progressive development.

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